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Milestone 20.5

REACHING OUT TO HARD-TO-SURVEY GROUPS AMONG THE POOR

Survey protocols, statistical
issues and research design

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of live or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1. A typology of hard-to-survey groups among the poor

Some specific populations can be harder to survey than the general population. In poverty research, immigrants, refugees or ethnic minorities, homeless people, children or households living in poverty, nomads, travellers, Roma, etcetera are frequently mentioned as hard-to-survey groups by the literature (Kalton, 2014). However, poor people are not hard-to-survey in general. Some groups are hard to sample (for instance homeless people), while others are hard to interview (for instance newly arrived migrants with an unknown mother tongue). The reasons explaining why these groups are harder to survey thus seem to vary. Benoit *et al.* (2005) identify three different difficulties which can make populations hard-to-reach: (1) there is no sample frame, because the group has an unknown size or is hard to define precisely; (2) it is difficult to acknowledge belonging to the group because membership involves dangers, such as being the object of hate or prosecution; and (3) members are less likely to reveal their identities, to cooperate or to give reliable answers about themselves or peers to researchers. In a same vein, Tourangeau (2014) has classified similar sources of difficulty, taking into account the different, sequential steps of the survey process. This results in a typology that distinguishes between populations (or members of these populations) which are *hard to sample*, *hard to identify*, *hard to find or to contact*, *hard to persuade* to participate and *hard-to-interview*.

In this chapter we present the typology of Tourangeau (2014) from the perspective of poverty. To what extent are poor people hard to survey? Which characteristics of the specific context in which poor people live, make them hard to survey? How can hard-to-survey groups of poor people nevertheless be reached, contacted, persuaded or interviewed and what sort of methodological choices are then required?

1.1 Hard-to-sample groups

By sampling groups, surveys aim either to estimate the size of the target group and its prevalence in the total population, or to study the characteristics of the target group. Most cited examples of hard-to-sample populations are rare populations and hidden populations. Rare populations represent only a small fraction of the frame population. Referring to Kish (1987), Kalton (2009) determines the size of 10% of the total population as the cut-off line between a minor (from 1 to 10% of the total population) and a major domain (more than 10% of the population). Surveys can however also aim to produce estimates for populations which comprise less than 1%, i.e. the mini-domains. Next to rare populations, hidden populations pose challenges to sampling. Cepeda and Valdez (2010) define hidden populations ‘as a subset of the general population whose membership is not readily distinguishable or enumerated on the basis of existing knowledge and/or sampling capabilities’.

Rare or hidden populations are hard to sample because of their small number or their unknown character, especially if there exists no separate sample frame that distinguishes the members of the target group from the general population. In that case, the sample cannot be simply drawn from that general list.

It is important to notice that poor households in general can hardly be considered as an example of a rare or even a hidden population. For the year 2011, in Europe, the share of poor households

far exceeds the cut-off line of 10% of the total European population. 24.1% of the European households meets one of the three criteria of the AROPE rate, the ‘at-risk-of-poverty-and-social-exclusion’ rate that was developed by the European Commission. Nevertheless, in his paper, Kalton (2014) lists a range of examples of hard-to-sample groups, in which some subgroups of poor populations are mentioned. In particular, children in poverty, homeless persons, immigrants and nomads can be classified as hard-to-sample groups with a high risk of poverty.

Chapter 2 deals with potential sampling difficulties related to research on hard-to-reach groups. Moreover, it gives an overview of the most important sampling methods for this kind of research such as disproportionate stratification, location sampling, capture-recapture methods and network-based sampling.

1.2 Hard-to-identify groups

When surveying specific groups, wider samples of respondents first need to be screened in order to ensure that subgroups can be identified as belonging to the target group. To meet this condition, it is necessary that the respondents or (household) informants are ‘both willing and able to answer the screening questions accurately’ (Tourangeau, 2014). Only then, a specific person or household can be correctly identified as a member of the target group.

However, not all groups are eager to be identified, due to stigma, sensitivity or motivated misreporting, resulting in research bias produced by undercoverage or underreporting of the specific group. For example, highly stigmatised groups, such as victims of human trafficking, may be reluctant to openly acknowledge that they meet the criteria or the relevant characteristics of the target group. Informants in their close neighbourhood are not always willing to answer the screening questions correctly. For example, Glasser *et al.* (2014) point out that in the US census homeless people are underreported because family or friends, who are hosting homeless relatives for a short or longer period, but who are tenants themselves, ‘would not want to risk jeopardising their housing by admitting that additional people are staying with them.’ The fear of losing welfare benefits or incurring some other penalty may thus lead to deliberately omitting of some household members. Tourangeau (2014) suggests that an anonymous rostering procedure should help to address this sort of concern.

Other reasons of misreporting are suspicion or distrust *vis-a-vis* outside researchers, and lack of interest in being researched (Lyberg *et al.*, 2014; Harkness *et al.*, 2014) In that respect, identifying hard-to-reach groups requires intensified efforts to establishing a climate of trust and mutual understanding between the researcher or research team and the respondents. Often mentioned strategies in establishing this trust and mutual understanding are the use of network-based methods, snowball sampling, community-based methods which seek partnering with organisations or services involved with the target group (for instance shelters/soup kitchen organisations for homeless people, Glasser *et al.*, 2014) and making screening instruments ‘culturally appropriate’ (Greenfields, 2009).

Next to reducing misreporting by the hard-to-reach groups, the accurate classification of individuals into a specific group by the researcher is critical. To that end, clear definitions of group characteristics are needed. Several authors (Volkert, 2006; Laderchi *et al.*, 2003; Schildrick & MacDonald, 2013) emphasise that the extent to which a household or an individual can be identified as belonging to the poor heavily depends on the definition and measurement approach used by the research team or by public institutions (such as the European Commission). Laderchi *et al.* (2003), for example, conclude in their comparative review of approaches to the identification and measurement of poverty that ‘there is no unique or ‘objective’ way of defining and measuring poverty. There is a large element of ‘construction’ involved in each of the poverty measures.’ In that respect, the choice for a specific approach can never be claimed as ‘neutral’ or totally ‘objective’, and will inevitably affect the sample construction and structure as well the research outcomes.

Laderchi *et al.* (2003) identify four dominant approaches to poverty measurement: the monetary approach, the capability approach, the social exclusion approach and the participatory methods. In

the monetary approach, the identification and measurement of poverty is based on uniform monetary metrics, i.e. income or expenditure data. Poverty is then considered as a shortfall in consumption or income from some poverty line, a minimum level of resources that people need to live. For example, the AROP rate (the at-risk-of-poverty rate of the European Commission) sets this poverty line separately for each member state at 60% of the median equalised disposable income in the state, weighted by the household size. According to this rate, 16.7% of all Europeans can be identified as belonging to the population with a high poverty risk (Eurostat, EU-SILC data 2013). Confronted with measurement problems that arose with the extension of the EU in 2004 (Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014) and influenced by the proposals of Atkinson *et al.* in 2002 (Volkert, 2006), the European Union decided to include non-monetary indicators that are based on multidimensional approaches such as the capability approach¹ (Volkert, 2006) or the social exclusion perspective² (Laderchi *et al.*, 2003). In this way, the European Commission took into account the central assumption of multidimensional approaches, namely, that ‘poor individuals generally experience various forms of deprivation, related not only to economic hardship, but also to social and environmental aspects.’ (Coromaldi & Zoli, 2012) In particular, this conceptual shift is expressed in the AROPE rate,³ the ‘at-risk-of-poverty-and-social-exclusion’ rate, in which two additional social exclusion indicators (material deprivation and joblessness at household level) are included. According to the AROPE criteria, the poverty rate in 2013 was extended from 16.7% (monetary approach) to 24.5% of European households meeting any of the three criteria (Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014, EC data from 2013). Using another approach to identify and measure poverty thus makes a real difference in determining which households must be considered for the sampling.

While multidimensional approaches have recently been incorporated by the EU social policy and the EU research, poverty research using participatory methods which take into account the views of poor people themselves, have remained marginal. However, in their qualitative research on ‘recurrent poverty’ in north-east England, Shildrick and MacDonald (2013) found that the interviewees’ own accounts and definitions of poverty are usually very much at odds with the (externally defined) standard poverty measures. Following the standard measures, four-fifths of their sample, consisting of 60 men and women living in two Middlesbrough estates of social housing, could be identified as ‘recurrently’ poor. Shildrick and MacDonald (2013) found, however, that ‘despite living in sometimes severe, material hardship interviewees denied that ‘poverty’ described their conditions of life.’ (see also Sime, 2008, for the same conclusion in research with children in poverty). According to Shildrick and MacDonald (2013), this refusal by people living in poverty to identify themselves as poor can, among other things, be explained as an outcome ‘of the long-standing stigma and shame of poverty in times of heightened “scrounger phobia” and as the evidence that the “ruling ideas” and political orthodoxies about “the undeserving poor” take hold, even amongst “the poor”.’

The discrepancy between the standard poverty measures (which are conventionally considered as more objective) and the interviewees’ ‘subjective’ accounts and definitions reveals some important issues related to the sample construction and screening. Firstly, the established discrepancy may create the impression that ‘objective’ and ‘subjective’ approaches cannot be seen as complementary parts in assessing poverty. According to Volkert (2006), however, assessing poverty exclusively with objective *or* subjective approaches will lead to inadequate poverty sampling and thus to targeting errors ‘since poverty is a phenomenon that implies value-driven *and* highly complex scientific aspects.’ He therefore suggests using a mix of both approaches. A similar view is adopted by Laderchi *et al.* (2006) who

1 The capability approach considers poverty as the inability to achieve certain minimal or basic capabilities. Sen (1993), the founder of this approach, defines basic capabilities as the ability to satisfy certain crucially important functionings up to certain minimally adequate levels. To identify the basic capability set of an individual, indicators assessing the personal characteristics (age, gender, physical capacities) and the general environmental context, are therefore included.

2 The European Foundation (2005) defines social exclusion as a ‘process through which individuals or groups are wholly or partially excluded from full participation in the society in which they live.’ Empirical research based on the social exclusion approach normally includes unemployment, access to housing, income, social contacts, lack of citizenship or democratic rights.

3 Next to the AROPE, this conceptual shift becomes clear in the EU SILC research that collects data on poverty which are based on an even wider set of criteria relating to education, housing, health, etc.

advocates the use of combined methods to identify and to target the poor, because of their ability to reflect the broad character of poverty.

Based on this use of combined methods, Alkire (2007) for example proposes some additional modules to standard survey instruments, namely on informal employment, empowerment, safety from violence, the ability to go without shame, and psychological and subjective well-being. Broadening the 'poverty' concept in this manner is a useful tool in diminishing the discrepancy between subjective and objective approaches. This strategy, however, does not take into account that the concept itself (poverty, homelessness, ...) may be inherently ambivalent. Denying this issue leads to undercounting, Martin (2007) argues, as this denial is built on the invalid assumption that 'each person can be uniquely and unambiguously attached to a household' and that the identification is consistent over a certain period of time. However, ethnographic research shows that homeless people, in fact, often cycle through various living arrangements and can be constantly on the move. For example, Glasser *et al.* (2014) found that the survey question in the US Census on the number of additional persons *living* in the household results in underreporting or undercounting, as household informants who are hosting homeless relatives or friends at the time of the census do not perceive their guests as living in their household, but as staying in their house, given the temporary character of the residence. Pre-testing the screening instruments within the target group can help to prevent such bias.

A last, ethical issue relating to the discrepancy between objective and subjective approaches is to which extent a research team should openly communicate that the research topic is on poverty (indicating that respondents have been identified as such already) or that the respondents are screened in order to identify them as poor. As long as poverty is considered as a stigmatising label, this kind of openness may indeed result in an identification refusal. If the research team instead chooses to pragmatically keep the silence about their research aim, ethical issues relating to trust and the right representation of the group may arise.

1.3 Hard-to-find or hard-to-contact groups

Another source of difficulty in surveys is that their members are hard to find (i.e. they include relatively high numbers that are never contacted), or hard to contact, i.e. they require high numbers of contact attempts.

According to Tourangeau (2014), in general, 'populations that are only loosely attached to a specific home or place are difficult to find', causing problems for population surveys and for longitudinal, or panel, surveys in particular. The most important reason for this loose attachment is mobility. Tourangeau (2014) identifies four types of mobile populations: traditionally nomadic cultures, itinerant minorities (such as gypsies in Europe or the Travellers in Ireland), persons who are temporarily mobile or displaced (such as recent immigrants, homeless persons, refugees) and persons at a mobile stage in their life cycle. Several populations within these types are traditionally seen as groups with a high risk of poverty, like Gypsies and Travelers, homeless people, refugees and recent immigrants. However, mobility or nomadism is not the only reason why groups are hard to locate or to contact. Next to their nomadic status, Travelers in Ireland, for example, are also hard to locate or to contact because they have 'been traditionally closed to outsiders' (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014). In order to prevent potential complaints about their presence, Gypsies decide to hide away so that local authorities and stakeholders may simply not be aware of their presence within their area (Brown & Scullion, 2009). Similar problems have been noticed in the case of homeless people. Glasser *et al.* (2014) for example report that some members of this subgroup do not want to be found, because they are hiding from the courts, the police or other authorities, or could not be found because they are living alone outdoors in separate, private places hidden from view. In a same vein, undocumented immigrants may prefer to be hidden, for fear of being caught and expelled.

In the examples above, groups have been called hard-to-find because of a specific characteristic of the group itself, such as mobility or distrust towards outsiders. Brown & Scullion (2010), however,

defend that this problem may also be caused by a lack of knowledge on behalf of the researcher on how, who, and where to contact certain groups or individuals. Finding caravan-based Gypsies, for example, is relatively uncomplicated because Gypsy caravan sites are in principle easily identifiable, while contacting this group poses real challenges.⁴ To avoid this type of non-response, the literature on this issue, in general, agrees that ‘finding and establishing meaningful contact can be a multi-faceted and intensive process, requiring pragmatism and flexibility on the part of the researcher’ (Brown & Scullion, 2010). In particular, when researching marginalised groups, traditional methods, such as advertising (flyers or posters), or standard letters have limited success. Multiple, innovative ways to access these groups are thus needed. A first frequently mentioned strategy is to find potential participants on specific locations or events (for instance soup kitchens in the case of homeless people, schools in the case of children in poverty, cf. location sampling). This strategy, however, requires that the right sites are accurately listed. By doing ethnographic research on homeless people, Glasser *et al.* (2014), for example, found out that the US Census had previously overlooked low cost hotels and motels as possible sites where homeless people could be found. Another widely adopted strategy for gaining access is working with gatekeepers, who may occur as the best or easiest first point of contact in order to enter a specific group. These gatekeepers can be found within the target group itself (such as the site manager or site resident of a caravan site where Gypsy Travellers reside) or within local community groups, service providers, health professionals, and education services who work or collaborate with the target group (for instance Homeless Networks, see Glasser, 2014). Several authors, however, note that using such gatekeepers is not without problems, as the researcher’s access to the target group becomes dependent on the gatekeeper’s choice of respondents (for a detailed overview of the advantages and problems of this strategy, see Chapter 4). Finally, several studies have built on previous efforts of other research groups or (health or social work) organisations to gain access. For the Ireland Traveller Health Study, Kelleher & Quirke (2014) explain how the first barrier of access to the Traveller community was overcome by utilising a network of already existing projects coordinated by a voluntary, non-governmental organisation, the Pavee Point Travelers Centres (‘Pavee Point’).

1.4 Hard-to-persuade groups

Getting contact with members of the target group is a necessary, but not a sufficient condition for participation, which requires to get the sampled person to agree to participate or to gain consent. Tourangeau (2014) identifies two potential sources of resistance to surveys: the sense of busyness and the falling levels of civic engagement. People who report to participate in activities such as community involvement, voting and volunteering are found to be more willing to participate in surveys than those who report low levels of involvement, voting and volunteering. According to Tourangeau (2014) this close relationship between involvement in these activities and involvement in surveys may be caused by an underlying ‘willingness to help others’.

Because poor people are often less involved in the community or in volunteering activities due to marginalisation or low self-esteem, it seems obvious to conclude that poor people are also less willing to participate in research. Other reasons explaining resistance to research participation are mistrust in research (leading to resistance to offer even minimal information about the family, see Sime, 2008), the (evidence-based) perception that participation has very little positive effect on their lives or fear that the research may cause potential harm, stigma, mistreatment or exploitation (Bonevski *et al.*, 2014; Brown & Scullion, 2010). Nicaise and Schockaert (2014), for example, indicate that even when undocumented migrants were found eventually, it was often not possible to get them involved as a result of their fear of being caught or expelled: ‘In many cases, we first needed to identify the sampled

⁴ This is, however, not the case for Gypsy-Travelers who reside within bricks and mortar accommodation. This group is less easy to find and to contact (see Brown & Scullion, 2010).

person's native language, and by the time an interpreter was found the person had disappeared or refused to collaborate'. Although some studies agree on the above reasons for refusing participation, a consensus that members of poor populations are, in general, less willing to participate in surveys, cannot be found in the literature. On the one hand, Heerweegh, Abts and Loosveldt (2007) found that correlates of poverty (migration status, single parenthood, tenancy status, inner city inhabitants) enhance non-response more than low income per se. On the other hand, Shildrick and MacDonald (2013), challenge this finding after their research with respondents in poor United Kingdom estates: 'The experience of doing the research was one that reminded us that 'hard to reach' is a label that sometimes wrongly applied to marginalised social groups. Very rarely did a potential interviewee decline to participate.' In that respect, the way of asking participation and the nature of the relationship between the researcher and the potential participant may occur as more critical than the characteristics of the target group. In the same vein, experienced interviewers from Belgium who participated in various surveys organised by BELSTAT pointed at the general distrust of low-educated individuals or the fact that requesting participation from tenants living in apartments or studio flats via an intercom more often results in refusal than face to face contacts with tenants of houses at the front door (Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014). In a same vein, Sime (2008) points at an element of unpredictability in contacts, experiencing that 'success often depended on the researcher's personal skills and ability to convince'.

The strategies mentioned in the literature to enhance participation are diverse, and consist of offering research participants a (financial) reward for their participation, paying professional workers to assist with recruitment, using multiple forms of contact for each participant (phone, mail, email address and other contact persons), using participant-centred approaches (use of personalised telephone calls or door-to-door-interviews instead of generic letters), culturally and linguistically appropriate participation letters, engaging peer interviewers, and training the interviewers so that they obtain the needed cultural competencies (see Chapter 4 for a detailed overview of these strategies).

1.5 Hard-to-interview populations

A last difficulty arises when respondents have been reached but appear to be hard to interview. Tourangeau (2014) identifies three reasons for this problem:

First, vulnerable people, such as children or prisoners may require consent from a parent, caretaker, director. In his study of children in poverty, Sime (2008) explains how adults' powerful position over children in school and at home or parental (school) disengagement may lead to an interview refusal independently of children's willingness and interest in being interviewed. A useful solution for this problem proved to be asking for a verbal instead of written consent, as parents living in poverty were found more responsive in phone conversations. From an ethical perspective, Mason and Gibson (2004) even challenge the requirement of a fully informed consent of a parent in favour of acting on children's consent, claiming, where 'children can understand the impact on them of participation ... such an approach (i.e., acting on children's consent) gives children the maximum opportunity to have their views and experiences recorded and avoids the risk of exclusion of children whose parents would not respond to a request'. Next to gaining consent, Sime (2008) also points at the problems that may arise from interviewing children in poverty at home. Not only can parents decide to cancel or just forget the pre-arranged visit as they were in the first place struggling to manage their household or complicated lives. They also may influence the data collection by insisting on being present during interviews and interfering in the interviewing process. In that case, Sime decided to consider these events with care in the analysis of the interviews.

Second, Tourangeau (2014) identifies individuals with cognitive or physical impairments, such as very ill people, persons with a mental handicap, deaf or blind people, as difficult or impossible to interview. Although these individuals are therefore left out of many surveys, according to Tourangeau

(2014), the high non-response rate of this group of individuals is only a minor problem when surveying the general population. However, if the target group of a survey is a subgroup where these problems are common, the high risks of non-response within these groups cannot be overlooked.

Third, individuals who may not speak, read or understand the language in which the survey questionnaire is written are hard to interview, even if they are willing to participate. Nicaise and Schockaert (2014) found that the complexity of the EU-SILC questionnaires had led to a relatively high number of breakoffs during interviews, indicating the need to simplify the questionnaires (for instance by offering the possibility of skipping certain questions) or the need for multiple revisions and a pre-pilot of the questionnaires within these groups before the official start of the interview process. O'Hegarty *et al.* (2010) explain how 'a strategic, targeted and carefully designed survey resulted in high response rates among Hispanic/Latino low-educated adults in border communities in Texas. In order to overcome the language barriers for a group with little or no knowledge of English, two teams of professional translators translated and cognitively tested the instrument in Spanish, while the interview itself was also conducted in Spanish. Next to these linguistic considerations, the questionnaires were modified in a culturally sensitive way and the interviewers were trained, all resulting in response rates (80%) that exceed other survey work today.

1.6 Conclusion

Using the framework of Tourangeau (2014), in this chapter, we showed which difficulties may arise when surveying hard-to-reach groups, in particular populations living in poverty. In general, the reasons that explain why these difficulties appear can be subsumed in three broad, but interrelated categories:

- as a result of specific characteristics of the target group (for instance mobility, linguistic barriers);
- as a result of the research design (for instance the use of ambivalent concepts, culturally inappropriate questionnaires) or;
- as a result of the interaction between researcher and (potential) respondent (for instance mistrust, communication problems).

In order to overcome these difficulties and to reach a hard-to-reach group living in poverty, researchers should carefully consider the aim and the design of their research and anticipate some ethical issues (for instance gaining consent of vulnerable groups), even before taking any steps in contacting the target group. Furthermore, the complex and multi-layered nature of the difficulties discussed above requires multiple, multidimensional and innovative strategies or approaches, not just showing respect for the respondents in an instrumental way (i.e. in order to obtain valid data), but also with the aim of improving the living conditions of poor populations or with the intention of giving them more voice and visibility in society. In that respect, we think, that the widely adopted strategies within this bulk of research do not coincidentally show a general shift to multidimensional, subjective and reflexive approaches or to survey methods in which members of the target group are actively engaged in the full research process (see also next chapters). As such, this sort of research must be considered as an important reference for creative, imaginative and innovative empirical research methods.

2. Sampling strategies

2.1 Introduction

Population sampling is the process of drawing a subset of subjects that is representative of the entire population. Sampling is done because it is impossible to test every single individual in the population, or simply save time, money and effort while conducting the research. In the ideal case, there is a complete and up to date list of the target population and the sample can be drawn from this list. However, this is rarely realised in practice: for most populations of interest in surveys, there is no list frame and sampling begins with some general purpose sampling frame, such as an area, address, or random-digit dial (RDD) frame. Alternative sampling methods, to overcome the lack of a complete sampling list are necessary in particular for 'hard-to-reach', 'elusive' and even 'mobile' populations as defined in the previous chapter. Major components of total survey error that specifically relate to these populations include sampling problems, such as the need for special sample frames. Often, there simply isn't any sampling frame, or a very incomplete one, that unavoidably yields biased results, for example where a survey on the health of homeless people is conducted only at health centres.

In the absence of a special frame, one reason why a population can be hard to sample is that its members are rare, representing a small fraction of the larger frame population. When subgroups of the target population are undercovered by available sample frames, an alternative sampling design must be developed. Even if the target population is not undercovered, using a sampling frame for the general population and screening down to the targeted subgroup may be inefficient and impractical due to cost. Dual or multiple frames or various referral sampling methods will often be needed to adequately and efficiently sample rare populations. What can be done for a given target population will vary greatly depending on what information is available to develop sampling frames. Apart from overall prevalence within the general population, there are two other population characteristics that affect the level of difficulty of sampling:

- the level of variation across areas or sampling strata in the prevalence of the rare subgroup. It is easier to find members of the rare population when a substantial proportion of them is concentrated in a small number of areas or strata that can be identified prior to sampling;
- the cost of a screening interview relative to the cost of the main interview. If screening interviews are relatively cheap (for instance: only a few questions are needed to identify members of the target population), then having to carry out a lot of them will not affect the final data collection costs that much.

Screening costs are high when tests or long series of questions are needed to identify members of the target population or when it is difficult to get people to complete the screener. Logically, sampling efficiency matters more when the screening process is expensive. In summary, a population is harder to sample as its overall prevalence becomes lower, as its prevalence varies less across the sampling strata, and as the screening costs increase relative to the cost of a main interview. Ideally, most of the rare target population falls within a few - or indeed a single high prevalence stratum and the screeners are relatively inexpensive (Tourangeau, 2014).

Each type of population involves particular difficulties for sampling. There are different analytic objectives for surveys of this diverse set of populations. With *static* populations, a main distinction is between surveys aiming to estimate the size of the population and its prevalence in the general population on the one hand, and surveys aiming to study the characteristics of the population on the other

hand. For example, is the main objective of the survey to estimate the proportion of children in poverty or to study the health, education, and housing conditions of poor children? With *mobile* populations, a key issue is whether the population of inference is the ‘visit’ or the ‘visitor’. For instance, is the population of inference the visits to shelters made by homeless or the homeless themselves?

Given the diversity of types of hard-to-sample populations, no single approach to sample design can fit all cases. According to Kalton (2014), questions such as the following need to be answered in narrowing down the range of design choices:

- How rare is the population? The challenges of sampling a target population that comprises one-hundredth of the general population are far greater than those for a target population that comprises one-tenth of the general population.
- How readily can members of the target population be identified? Is the target population a ‘hidden’ population, with many of its members reluctant to admit to that membership in a survey setting?
- Is there a large-scale survey that can serve as a screener sample for identifying members of the target population?
- Is the target population more concentrated in some parts of the sampling frame? If so, using disproportionate stratification to oversample those parts may be effective.
- Are there one or more partial sampling frames (generally list frames) of the hard-to-sample population that are available for use in sampling? If so, selecting the sample from more than one frame may be effective.
- Is the target population accessible by sampling households? Special techniques are needed to sample the homeless and nomads, frequently involving some form of location sampling (Kalton, 2014).

The following section will discuss different sampling methods that are used for hard-to-sample populations. Particular attention will be paid to methods suitable to sample populations in poverty related research.

2.2 Sampling methods

The question of sampling hard-to-reach populations partly overlaps with that of rare populations for whom there is generally no sampling frame. A review of techniques allowing this type of population to be sampled was recently undertaken by Kalton. It was shown that a variety of methods can be used to sample hard-to-reach groups (Kalton, 2014). Generally, a distinction can be made between probability sampling methods on the one hand and nonprobabilistic sampling on the other hand.

A probability sampling method utilises some form of random selection. In order to have a random selection method, a procedure must be set up which ensures that the different units in the population have equal probabilities of being selected. However, in most cases this method can only be used when a complete sampling frame is available, which means that one has (contact) information for the entire population. It requires that the population is fairly stable and easily identifiable, which is not the case for homeless people, for example. For some hard-to-reach target groups, a special form of random sampling can be used to (partly) overcome this problem: With *stratified random sampling*, the population is divided into homogeneous subgroups in order to take a simple random sample in each subgroup. It ensures that key subgroups of the population, such as small minority groups, will be represented. When the subgroup is extremely small, different sampling fractions can be used within the different strata to randomly over-sample the small group. When different sampling fractions are used in the strata, the method is called *disproportionate random sampling*.

In general, researchers prefer probabilistic or random sampling methods because they are considered to be more accurate and rigorous. With a probabilistic sample, the odds or probability that the population is represented well is known and it is possible to estimate confidence intervals for the statistic. However, in applied research there may be circumstances where it is not feasible, practical,

or theoretically sensible to apply random sampling. This is often the case for the hard-to-reach groups of interest. As a result, a wide range of *nonprobabilistic* alternatives, such as snowball sampling or capture-recapture sampling, are used to study these groups. The difference between nonprobability and probability sampling is that nonprobability sampling does not involve random selection (e.g. when minority households are selected via intermediaries). Consequently, it is possible that the population is not adequately represented. Moreover, it will often be hard to know how well the target population is represented. However, the specific characteristics of the hard-to-reach groups often force researchers to use these alternative methods which are more suitable for these target populations (Trochim, 2006).

This section will give an overview of the most popular techniques used to sample hard-to-reach populations. Besides a general description of the method, possible strengths and weaknesses of each method will be presented. If possible, (good) practices of the use of the methods in poverty related research will be discussed as well.

2.2.1 Disproportionate stratification

Some rare populations are more heavily concentrated in certain segments of the population. When this concentration occurs, it can be advantageous to oversample the segments with the heavier concentrations. Thus the various segments of the population are treated as strata.

2.2.1.1 Method

The disproportionate stratification method concentrates the sample in segments of the population where the rare population is more prevalent. It requires that segments of the population with greater concentrations can be identified in the survey's sampling frame so that they can be treated as strata for oversampling.

There are different approaches for applying disproportionate stratification in sampling certain minorities. One of the most well-known types of this sampling method is geographical stratification, which is often used when sampling minority populations that tend to cluster geographically. With face-to-face interviewing and area sampling, segments can be assigned to strata based on their prevalence of the target population. Another approach for applying disproportionate stratification in sampling minorities is to form the strata based on last names. With a sample drawn from a list of names, the method involves identifying names that are likely to be from the minority under study. A third method is to stratify units according to ratings provided by field staff. The method can sometimes be immediately applied, as with geographical stratification. In other cases, its application requires innovative ways to construct the strata.

2.2.1.2 Evaluation

When applied appropriately, disproportionate stratification can improve the efficiency of sample design for a hard-to-sample population, although the gains in efficiency are often modest. The most common misapplication is to focus on the sample size achieved, without accounting for the unequal selection probabilities associated with the disproportionate stratification. Rather, the focus should be on the effective sample size that takes into account the loss of precision in the survey estimates arising from the unequal weights needed to compensate for the unequal selection probabilities. The focus on sample size rather than effective sample size can, for instance, lead to a strong oversampling of strata with a high prevalence of the rare population, while they cover just a small proportion of that population.

As was noted by Kalton and others, if element variances and data collection costs are roughly equal across the strata and simple random samples are drawn within each stratum, disproportionate allocation significantly improves the precision of the survey estimates only when three conditions are satisfied: (1) the prevalence of the target population needs to be much higher in the oversampled strata;

(2) the proportion of the target population that falls in the oversampled data needs to be high; and (3) the per-unit cost of the survey data collection needs to be high relative to the screening cost. In many cases, however, not all three conditions above are met and the gains in precision under the optimal allocation of the sample across the strata are not large. Moreover, the optimal allocation requires knowledge of the proportions of the members in each stratum who are in the target population, as well as the cost of identifying and collecting the survey data from members of the target population relative to the cost of screening out a non-member. Using inaccurate estimates of these quantities reduces the precision gains and it can even lead to a loss in precision. If compiling the data needed to allocate the population members to the strata is costly, this approach may not be cost-effective (Kalton, 2014).

2.2.1.3 Disproportionate stratification in practice

The disproportionate stratification sampling method has been frequently used to study migrant populations who are concentrated in inner-city areas. For surveys on poverty in general, geographical areas can be classified first into high-, medium- and low-income areas, with the latter being oversampled. However, as noted earlier, the method is less suitable to study subgroups such as the homeless because of the lack of a decent sampling frame.

2.2.2 Location sampling

In the case of mobile or ‘elusive’ populations that are not easily linked to a single place (such as the homeless and migrant workers), the best strategy often involves ‘indirect sampling’, i.e. sampling places or services where the members of the elusive population are likely to be encountered rather than sampling the members of the population directly (Kalton, 2014).

2.2.2.1 Method

The general condition is that the population of interest visits a certain number of places that, conversely, are not often visited by the rest of the population. In case of the homeless, these places can be shelters, services providing meals, accommodation, clean clothes, etc. These places can be sampled after an exhaustive list has been made of them, and then a sample can be taken of the persons visiting those places. However, attention must be paid to the number of times when the target population visits the premises (Trochim, 2006).

In essence, location sampling is sampling visitors to specified locations. The technique can be used to sample either the population of *visits* or the population of *visitors* to these locations. Whereas sampling visits is relatively straightforward, sampling visitors is far more challenging: it requires assessing the extent of coverage of the target population (the probability of each individual to visit a given location) as well as accounting for the multiple routes of selection for visitors who visit different locations during the period of data collection.

Sampling visits

Relevant applications in poverty research include surveys of the clientele of homeless shelters and soup kitchens as a strategy for capturing homeless. In all these cases, visitors making multiple visits have greater chances of selection for the sample. Given that the visit itself is the unit of analysis, no weighting adjustment needs to be made for multiple visits.

Sampling visitors

Location sampling has been used to sample a variety of hard-to-sample populations. The general requirement is that a set of locations can be identified such that a high proportion of the target population will visit one or more of these locations during the data collection period. Whereas the general designs for sampling visitors are based on designs for sampling visits, there are important

differences. With the visitor as the unit of analysis, the unequal probability of visits across individuals during the data collection period must be taken into account. Moreover, given that sampling is likely to continue for some period of time on the one hand and that such populations are mobile on the other hand, members may also have multiple chances for selection (Kalton, 2014). The Generalised Weight Share Method (GWSM) allows an unbiased estimator to be established by taking into account the different probabilities of inclusion in the sample. At the design stage, the objective must be to create a combination of the most parsimonious list and the shortest possible time interval that has high coverage since that will help to control for multiple chances of selection. Location sampling is widely used to sample populations that have no fixed abode for both censuses and surveys: homeless persons may be sampled at shelters and at soup kitchens when they go for food (Trochim, 2006); undocumented immigrants may be sampled at police stations when they are arrested; or travellers at camping sites where they reside temporarily.

2.2.2.2 Evaluation

One of the main downsides of location sampling is that establishing and updating the list (of the places visited and the times at which they are visited) is often time-consuming and costly. Where a high proportion of the population of interest does not visit these places or does so only very rarely, it can lead to a coverage bias. Moreover, there may be data collection problems associated with the places due to refusal by managers/owners, rapid departure of users/clients, etc.

In the case of sampling visitors, calculating the weights for individuals (e.g. using the weight share method) requires the inclusion of specific questions about attendance of these places. This relies on the individual's memory and may induce errors. Moreover, if multiple use is not duly accounted for, once again the estimators will be biased (Trochim, 2006).

2.2.2.3 Location sampling in practice

Time-location sampling has been used for surveys on homeless persons that have been carried out in France since 1995. The surveys were based on indirect sampling with the places in which the survey was conducted comprising a sample of the locations where services aimed essentially at the homeless are provided (depending on the case, shelters, kitchens, reception centres, outreach teams, etc.). The sampling frame includes several stages. The method consists of taking a sample from the entire set of services provided by the meal and accommodation services on one survey day. The various sampling stages were as follows:

- selecting the cities (for a national survey);
- selecting the services and days for the survey in the sampling frame;
- selecting the individuals through the services they use in each service selected.

The step from services to persons is undertaken through a set of weightings calculated according to the weight share method. These surveys require drawing up an exhaustive list of the locations concerned and call for a high investment from interviewers who must select the persons to be interviewed.

The precision of the data partly depends on how the managers of the services perceive the survey and therefore, there are limits from the very first stages of constructing a sampling frame. Moreover, since each service may address a particular type within the populations studied, it is essential to keep refusals by the services to participate in the survey to a minimum. Ensuring that the managers of the associations fully understand the survey's objectives is therefore essential. Another important element for the calculation of the weightings is the retrospective sections of the questionnaire relating to the various services visited over the previous days. The quality of the replies largely depends on the capacity of persons to remember their time use in the week preceding the survey and the possibility of unambiguously identifying each service visited (Quaglia & Vivier, 2010).

The approach can be illustrated with the ENFAMS survey conducted in 2013 by the Observatoire du Samusocial de Paris (Enfants et familles sans logement) among homeless children and families. The objectives of this study were to estimate the size of this population in the Paris region, to describe their socio-demographic characteristics and to evaluate their health status and needs. The survey was based on a sample of 801 families provided with accommodation in emergency centres, long-term rehabilitation centres, social hostels and centres for asylum seekers.

The sample for the ENFAMS survey was collected based on a time-location sampling design. In a first stage, an exhaustive list of all services accommodating homeless families in the Paris region was created. Data on the number of the sheltered families and the number of minor children within each service were collected through a telephone survey. The type of the service, its distance from Paris and its distance to a train station were taken into account in stratifying the sampling frame into 36 strata. Farthest transport zones and emergency shelters were oversampled, whereas asylum centres and social hostels were under-sampled. In a second stage, families were selected using simple random sampling in each selected service. During the third and final stage, one child was randomly chosen in each family among all those younger than 13 years (Vandentorren *et al.*, 2015).

2.2.3 Capture-recapture methods

If the main goal of the survey is to estimate the size of the population, capture-recapture methods can be used. In these methods, at least two samples are drawn, which ideally are completely independent from each other. The estimated size of the population is based on the proportion of cases found in both samples. There have been some applications to the homeless, mainly in the United Kingdom under the name of the contact-recontact method.

2.2.3.1 Method

A vital assumption for the capture-recapture method to be successfully used is that the population remains stable over the observation period, i.e. that there will not be any new members or departures of old ones. The technique is based on at least two independent observations (or sources) of this population. In order to estimate the size N of the target population, the number of members of the population observed the first time (n), the number of persons observed the second time (m) and the number of persons observed on both occasions (M) need to be known. N is then estimated by calculating $(n*m)/M$. The persons have to be identified (by whatever identifier) in order to be 'recognised' in M on the second occasion (for more details about the deduction of the formula, see Brittain & Böhning, 2009).

Figure 2.1 The capture-recapture method

Source Marpsat and Razafindratsima (2010)

In the case of homeless persons, the observations are made, for instance, where homeless make use of services. They then fill out a brief questionnaire at each visit to one of the centres observed. The questionnaires are anonymous but an identifier is used that allows the persons re-contacted to be identified (Trochim, 2006).

2.2.3.2 Evaluation

While this method's underlying concept is simple, the conditions that must be met in order for the model to remain valid are fairly restrictive:

- first condition: the observation must be collected in such a way that all individuals in the population have the same chance of being selected in each period. In the case of the homeless, the population of interest may be extremely heterogeneous in its characteristics and also its behaviour. For instance, if the use of particular services varies across subgroups of the homeless population, the groups that use them less will be under-covered. This may induce bias if *either* the profile of visitors *or* their probability of recapture are different;
- second condition: the observations on two different occasions are independent. This assumption is violated, for instance, if providers of the two services refer clients to each other. Imperfections in the sampling frame can also lead to correlation bias;
- third condition: the reference population does not change between two contacts or captures, i.e. the population remains fixed (which is definitely not the case with homeless people). This condition can only be relaxed if the two samples are investigated within the same short time span. When there are changes in the reference population, the use of the simplest model also leads to bias.

Another difficulty may derive from the differences in definition (e.g. the homeless: roofless only or also people using shelters?) in different sources. A filter questionnaire may then improve the coherence between definitions.

2.2.3.3 Capture-recapture sampling in practice

In order to estimate the number of homeless persons in the United Kingdom, Williams (2010) used the capture-recapture method. He applied the method in Torbay and Plymouth, where the number of homeless people was estimated on the basis of their visits to various services intended for them. In these studies, the geographical factor was beneficial for the research targets. Both urban areas were surrounded by countryside with a low population density and the sea, thus making movement in and out of the areas into adjoining neighbourhoods somewhat easier to control for.

In capture-recapture samples, individuals should be reliably 'tagged'. In these studies, this was achieved through four identifiers: sex, date of birth, where staying at present, and length of time (converted into days) spent in either study location (Plymouth or Torbay). In most agencies these data could be taken straight from agency records, but in addition a standard monitoring form was completed.

Although the homeless are a target group that is ill-defined and very mobile, which makes it even more difficult to enumerate, the Plymouth and Torbay research was considered a success. It used a hybrid model that combined a simple two-capture approach, but repeated three times over a one year period (providing a total of six captures in each location). The longitudinal element provided important data on process, also because the results of each set of captures in each location varied little from the mean, thus indicating some level of measurement reliability. If there had been much variance between the models, the conclusion would have been one of important measurement error or environmental changes (Williams, 2010).

2.2.4 Network-based sampling

In studies of hidden and hard-to-reach human populations, a variety of research methods and practices have been developed over a number of decades to enable better understanding of the individual behaviours and social dynamics of the community of interest. The approaches developed include enabling the researcher to become an active and trusted participant in the community under study and the members of the community to become active participants in the research. Because of this process, recruitment methods have evolved that trace social links or relationships in the community, which allows the researcher to penetrate more deeply and become more substantially integrated with the community. These methods are called network-based sampling or chain-referral methods. Their purpose is to collect demographic information about hard-to-reach groups by reaching members of these groups through their own social networks. Some network-based approaches, such as respondent-driven sampling, recruit respondents directly from other respondents' networks, making the sampling mechanism similar to a stochastic process on the social network.

Although there are a number of reported applications of network sampling, it has not been widely used. According to Kalton (2014), an important limitation is the risk that the sampled informant may not accurately report the target population status of other members of the linkage, either deliberately or through lack of knowledge. Additionally, ethical issues can arise when sampled persons are asked about the target population membership of those in their linkage, particularly when that membership is a sensitive matter.

Snowball sampling, and its more recent outgrowth respondent-driven sampling (RDS) are the most popular forms of network sampling intended to reduce the problems of identifying members of rare or stigmatised populations. They will be presented in the section below.

2.2.4.1 Methods

Snowball sampling

Snowball sampling was originally used as a method for selecting a sample of the members of a social network, such as groups of friends at a school. A random sample of network members was selected.

This initial sample was used to identify other members of the network. Over time, however, snowball sampling emerged as a nonprobability approach to sampling design and inference in hard-to-reach, or equivalently, hidden populations. As suggested above, sampling these populations is difficult because standard statistical sampling methods require a list of population members (i.e. the sampling frame) from which the sample can be drawn. This alternative nonprobability form of snowball sampling became a widely employed method in qualitative research on hard-to-reach populations.

Snowball sampling begins with a convenience sample of initial subjects. These subjects serve as ‘seeds’, through which wave 1 subjects are recruited. Wave 1 subjects in turn recruit wave 2 subjects and the sample subsequently expands wave by wave like a snowball growing in size as it rolls down a hill. This process continues until the desired sample size is obtained or the survey period is over.

Many studies of hard-to-reach populations have relied on a fairly simple and inexpensive convenience sampling method such as ‘snowball sampling’. The main critique is that this method produces biased samples because respondents who have a large number of social connections are able to provide researchers with a higher proportion of other respondents who most likely have characteristics similar to that initial respondent. The result is a final sample that over-represents respondents with more social connections and underrepresents those with fewer social connections, usually the more hidden group members. This limitation produces a sample from which no accurate statistical inference can be made to the larger target population (Johnston & Sabin, 2010)

The use of snowball sampling in research on hidden hard-to-reach populations created a widespread perception of snowball sampling in particular and chain-referral methods in general as conventional sampling methods. In an article on problems of inference from chain data on hidden populations, Erickson states that the sample begins with a convenience sample with bias of unknown magnitude and unknown direction. Then, this bias is compounded in unknown ways as the sample expands from wave to wave. Thus, the main critique is that chain-referral samples were inherently limited to convenience samples. The judgment that chain-referral sampling is a convenience method was challenged in a series of papers and led to the development of a new method for collecting and analysing chain-referral data, respondent driven sampling (Heckathorn, 2011).

Respondent-driven sampling

Respondent-driven sampling (RDS) is a sampling design in which members of the hidden population are enlisted to do the actual sample recruitment based on their social connections. It can be seen as an advanced version of snowball sampling. However, unlike snowball sampling, RDS allows unbiased estimators to be produced under certain conditions. The method evolved incrementally in a series of papers which expanded and strengthened it. Because a different form of the method was presented in each paper, the term RDS refers not to a single method, but to a series of methods that share as their common core an effort to convert chain-referral sampling into a sampling method of good estimability.

In the initial paper, it was shown that, contrary to conventional wisdom, bias from the convenience sample of initial subjects (seeds) is progressively attenuated as the sample expands wave by wave. The model approaches an equilibrium that is independent from the starting point and thus independent from the convenience sample of seeds from which it begins. The implication is that this sampling method can become reliable if the number of waves is sufficiently large. This would mean that any selection of seeds may ultimately produce the same equilibrium sample composition (Heckathorn, 2011).

The basic method of RDS sampling involves the selection of an initial sample or set of ‘seeds’ from a hard-to-reach population by some design or convenience procedure (Johnston, 28 April 2014). Subject to satisfying screening interview criteria, each seed is given some number of coupons to be used in recruiting new members of the hard-to-reach population. The recruiter gives the coupons (one each) to members of the target population known to him or her. In this way the coupons are tracing links. A coupon carries a double incentive. If the potential recruit comes in to be interviewed

and satisfies the screening interview, he or she receives a (monetary) incentive. Additionally, the recruiter is given a reward for the recruit coming into the sample. Any of the recruits may in turn be given a set of coupons with which to recruit additional members of the population to sample. As such, the process continues for a desired number of waves or a target sample size. As with location-sampling, the probability of selecting each individual is not known a priori and the weightings are calculated a posteriori, after collection (Thompson, 2014).

Four elements must be present for a method to constitute genuine RDS:

1. it must be possible to trace who recruited whom (with the assistance of a number or bar code appearing on the coupon);
2. to establish the weightings, it is necessary to collect information concerning the size of each person's network;
3. there must be a maximum number of possible recruitments for one and the same person, generally up to three, which reduces the recruitment differences between individuals who have a wider network and others who have just a small one;
4. the recruiter and the recruit must have known each other prior to the recruitment, each being a member of the other's social network (Marpsat & Razafindratsima, 2010).

If these assumptions are met, the members of the hidden population are not hidden to each other, but only to members outside the population. However, even if members of the hidden population know each other, this does not mean that they are willing to reveal each other to the researchers. Furthermore, it remains to be seen how often these and the other assumptions on which RDS rests are met in practice and how robust the method is when its assumptions are violated (Tourangeau, 2014).

2.2.4.2 Evaluation

Network sampling is useful for gathering quantitative data from large samples of hard-to-reach and hidden populations. No sampling frame is needed. Furthermore, the method allows participants to remain anonymous and the fact that peers recruit peers might be beneficial to overcome obstacles such as stigma, discrimination and lack of trust (Johnston, 28 April 2014). Moreover, the method allows for face-to-face contact of researchers with members of hard-to-reach groups, facilitating exhaustive interviews. However, the price for an entry to these groups is high as RDS uses a specially designed link-tracing framework for sampling. Estimates from RDS are also biased because of the network structure captured during selection, with much statistical work surrounding RDS being intended to re-weigh RDS observations to have properties resembling a simple random-sample (McCormick & Zheng, 2014).

Though methods such as RDS can be advantageous, financial and logistic challenges often prevent researchers from employing these methods, especially on a large scale. Persons with a poor social network have a lower probability of being reached. Moreover, it is necessary to verify whether each person recruited is a member of the population of interest. This is not easy for all populations and may be intrusive. With network sampling, the informant is asked to provide screening data for other persons linked to the informant in a clearly defined way living elsewhere. A key requirement is that every member of the linkage must know and be willing to report on the target population membership of all those linked to them, a factor that influences the choice of linkages. In some cases, the original informant is able to provide the survey data for each of the members of the target population that he or she had identified. However, the informant must know and be willing to report the data, which can be problematic in terms of accuracy and/or sensitivity. Mostly, the survey data must be obtained from the target population members themselves, in which case the informant must be able

and willing to provide accurate contact information for the target population members. Other obstacles might be the difficulty to estimate the refusal rate given that refusals are made to the recruiter, and the complexity of the specific data-collection organisation.

2.2.4.3 Network based sampling in practice

Although the network based sampling techniques are mostly known for studying highly stigmatised target groups such as drug users, HIV patients and homosexuals, the method has also been used in poverty related research. David and Snijders (2002) used the snowball sampling method to estimate the size of the homeless population in Budapest, Hungary. Although homelessness is a relatively new issue in Hungary, the problems that social policy makers have to face are the same as anywhere else. In order to make any decisions they want to know numbers. One of the methods used to estimate the size of the homeless population in Budapest was snowball sampling.

For the research, homeless persons were asked whether they knew other homeless people by name. The type of relation was also asked for. Since this population is quite segregated, not only from the non-homeless population but internally as well, the rate of those who could mention any other homeless person was low: only 29% of the respondents could give full names of the persons nominated by them. Most people listed by the respondents were from the same place where they themselves usually appear or spend the night. Although the sample size seemed much larger than necessary, the researchers were aware of a potential underestimation of the total size given that there can be gathering places which were not surveyed by them and which are totally unconnected to the places that were surveyed. In order to get a more reliable estimate with a snowball method, the researchers suggest that the sites of the survey should be chosen even more carefully. Not just the number of the different (quasi-independent) sites that is important but rather the type of that site. For instance, future research using this method should sample places such as hospitals where the chance for homeless people to be independent of each other is higher than in a shelter or in a soup kitchen (David & Snijders, 2002).

2.2.5 A combination of methods

In many case studies a combination of sampling methods is used to study hard-to-reach groups. In what follows, a study to identify rough sleepers and homeless people will be presented for which the researchers used a combination of location sampling and snowball sampling.

Although the EU Survey of Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) contains a wealth of information, problems arise with the poverty measures as a result of the difficulty in reaching the poor in general. For this reason, the Belgian Combat Poverty Service commissioned research on the gaps and potential quality improvements in these poverty statistics for Belgium. One of the main purposes of the research was the identification of groups with a relatively high poverty risk that were not included in the EU-SILC for various reasons. A complementary pilot survey was carried out among two selected population groups that either do not form part of the sampling frame of the EU-SILC or do not live at their official residence: rough sleepers and homeless people, and undocumented immigrants. These groups were selected because of their high level of obscurity, their relative size and their unusually high level of deprivation. The main purpose was to collect data that would allow the researchers to compare the living conditions of these groups with those of other poor households and with the cross-section of Belgian households. In what follows, we will focus on the sampling method that was used for rough sleepers and homeless people.

The target was to interview 250 homeless people. The two-stage sampling process, which began with the selection of intermediaries, involved a risk of missing the most marginalised people in the target group, in particular rough sleepers. Consequently, 15% of the interviews were conducted in the street, in stations or abandoned buildings and thus, it can be seen as an application of the location sampling method. Snowball sampling was also tried out but yielded very few contacts (5%). In the

case of rough sleepers, snowballing appeared to be redundant because there was enough direct access to other respondents. For the bulk of the data collection, the researchers collaborated with third sector organisations in order to have easier access to a sufficient number of respondents. Quota were set per region on the basis of different sources that provided approximate information such as the registers of the associations of shelters for the homeless people. Homeless people appeared easier to reach in Flanders than in Wallonia and Brussels; female and young homeless were (presumably) underrepresented.

During the sampling process, compromises were made. A balance was sought in the sampling between scientific criteria and practical feasibility. For instance, the researchers' initial protocol to interview the persons on a list or the person entering a shelter based on a specific interval was abandoned for a more realistic procedure whereby persons under the influence of drugs or alcohol, or with severe psychological disorders were screened out (Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014).

3. Problems resulting from inadequate inclusion of hard-to-reach groups

3.1 Introduction

The main problems of data unreliability and bias with respect to hard-to-reach populations are related to the absence or underrepresentation of certain groups. Decreasing participation in surveys generally leads to reduced data reliability because of reduced sample size, and, more specifically, may increase coverage errors and non-response bias in the likely event that the profile of non-contacts and refusals systematically differs from that of respondents. In some cases, it is possible to address the problem of underrepresentation through weighting and non-response adjustments. In some cases, however, these techniques can raise problems of their own: unreliable or outdated census data induce weighting errors and reduced hard-to-reach respondent subsamples may not be representative of the whole hard-to-reach group. As a result, they just offer a partial solution at best.

The extent of the bias and error that can emerge will obviously vary, depending on context, method and purpose. It depends on the relative size of the hard-to-reach group population, its heterogeneity, as well as the survey methods (Behrens *et al.*, 2008).

This chapter will discuss the aforementioned problems of non-response and coverage given that research on hard-to-reach populations is extremely sensitive to such errors. Besides non-response and coverage error, the difficulties regarding undercounts will be treated. Alongside an overview of each problem in the specific context of hard-to-reach poor populations, measures aimed at reducing the errors will be discussed.

3.2 Non-response error

3.2.1 Problem

Non-response errors result from a failure to collect complete information on all units in the selected sample. Non-response occurs when sampled individuals do not respond to a survey at all (unit non-response) or do not respond to specific questions in a questionnaire (item non-response). Unit non-response arises for example because no contact can be established with the unit, because of the unit's refusal to participate the survey or because s/he is unable to respond properly. Item non-response arises when some data are collected for a unit but values of specific items are missing, for example because the respondent refuses to answer a sensitive question or is unable to provide the answer to a question requiring complex information.

Non-response *bias* occurs when members of the target population who fail to respond are different on variables of interest from members who do respond (Lyberg *et al.*, 2014). Thus, non-response errors affect survey results in two ways. First, the decrease in sample size or in the amount of information collected in response to a particular question results in larger standard errors. Secondly, and perhaps more importantly, a bias is introduced to the extent that non-respondents differ from respondents within a selected sample. When response rates differ across groups in a survey, this is also not too serious as long as the reasons for nonresponse are not related to the topic of the survey.

Only when the non-response is related to the topic of the survey, it cannot be ignored. High non-response rates tend to leave ample space for such bias (Stoop, 2005).

3.2.2 Measures to reduce non-response error

Measures that can be taken to reduce non-response among hard-to-reach groups are discussed in terms of data collection protocols, recruitment techniques and non-response follow up.

With respect to *data collection protocols*, response rates can be increased by expanding the period over which data is collected in the case of cross-sectional surveys. Increasing the required number of attempts to make contact also increases the chance of contacting hard-to-reach respondents. Interviewer teams are sometimes assisted by 'tracker teams' who systematically track potential respondents who appear to be hard to contact. And, needless to say, questionnaires should take into account the skills of respondents and the interview circumstances, avoiding excessive complexity and language barriers. Whenever possible (and relevant), surveys should be conducted in the languages of all population groups.

With regard to *recruitment techniques*, a variety of measures can be taken to provide advance warning of scheduled contacts, and incentivise response. Advance warning of scheduled contacts has been shown to result in increased response rates. This can be achieved through media campaigns or letters which are customised to the hard-to-reach groups. Moreover, incentives are becoming more common in all kinds of surveys, ranging from small pre-incentives to lotteries. However, the incentive should be carefully designed so that the impact effectively raises the response rates of the hardest-to-reach groups – at minimum cost (Behrens *et al.*, 2008).

Regarding the *non-response follow-up*, analysis of non-response should occur early in the survey process, so that patterns of, and reasons for, non-response can be identified with sufficient time to make any necessary changes to the survey protocol. Techniques have been developed with the explicit aim of minimising non-response error and providing data for correcting non-response error by adjusting for refusal. Follow-up surveys among refusers (double sampling) and the central question procedure can be used to discover whether and how non-respondents differ from respondents:

- dual sampling implies approaching the complete sample using an inexpensive survey mode and settling for moderate response rates, and subsequently drawing a sample from the non-respondents, approaching them with an expensive mode and achieving complete cooperation among this sub-sample. The method was used in a postal survey among disabled people living in private households where the initial response was 81%. From the 19% refusers, a 10% sample was drawn which yielded an 82% response rate. Although the method can be helpful in reducing non-response bias, its use is relatively limited due to substantial additional costs of the follow-up interviews and the potential delay in completing the fieldwork;
- the central question method implies that all non-respondents are asked to answer one question central to the survey, either at the doorstep or by post or telephone, assuming a high response rate on this central question. The same question should be asked in the regular survey, preferably as early as possible to prevent other, more detailed questions influencing the replies. This method is relatively inexpensive and can in many cases be used when cooperation is denied. It is particularly useful when response is related to whether or not people see the survey as relevant to them. Potential problems are that the survey should have a 'central' question and that it might be difficult to re-contact the non-respondents of populations that are already hard to reach (Stoop, 2005).

The two principal methods used to *correct for bias* due to non-response and to make efficient use of data are weighting and imputation. Weighting is classically used to treat the problem of unit non-response, whereas imputation is mostly used to treat problems of item non-response.

Weighting is a unit-level adjustment, providing a common form of adjustment for all analyses based on a common set of responding units and is thus natural for the treatment of unit non-response. It is less practical to use weighting to treat item non-response, since a different method of weighting would be required for each subset of variables (Laaksonen *et al.*, 2004). Rather than accepting a poor match between the sample and the population, it is now common for survey data-sets to use weights to bring the two more closely into line. This is known as ‘non-response weighting’.

The weighting method was used to tackle the non-response error in a survey which aimed to better understand the homeless population in France. Since there was no survey frame to allow direct access to homeless persons, the survey principle involved sampling the services they received and interviewing the individuals who used those services. Weighting the individual input to the survey proved difficult because a single individual could receive several services within the designated reference period. Pilot surveys showed that non-response rates varied widely depending on the type of service used. The reweighting of respondents therefore used weights by service centre. Moreover, some individuals were sampled several times in different service centres. Such individuals might respond the first time but not the second, thus producing a ‘false non-response’. If this was not detected, the total non-response adjustment would have led to incorrect reweighting. To avoid this problem, the interviewers always tried to find out the reason for the refusal and checked off a specific box when the individual stated that s/he had already been interviewed (Ardilly & Le Blanc, 2001).

Imputation is a variable-specific adjustment and is a popular method to treat missing data for a given variable. Each missing value is replaced by an imputed (fabricated) value. If the values of auxiliary variables x are available for cases with missing values of y , and if x and y are correlated, then it will often be possible to reduce the bias by imputing values for y using the observed x values. Imputation tends to become more complicated and time consuming as the number of variables with missing values increases. The standard approach under imputation is to treat the imputed values in the completed dataset as if they were actual values. Imputation methods are generally designed so that this approach will lead to a less biased estimator than would arise if cases with missing values were simply deleted. The most common approach produces just one imputed value for each missing item, which is called single imputation. An alternative method is to replace each missing value with a set of plausible values, reflecting the uncertainty about the right value to impute (multiple imputation). These multiply imputed data sets are then analysed by using standard procedures for complete data and combining the results from these analyses. This results in valid statistical inference that properly reflects the uncertainty due to missing values (Laaksonen *et al.*, 2004).

In a study on longitudinal outcomes for youth receiving runaway/homeless shelter services, the imputation of missing data was required due to substantial attrition (approximately 20-30% per time period) and missing data within individual interviews. Missing data were replaced by multiple imputation to create an analytic sample of 371 individuals. Complete datasets were created from the original data. Data were then analysed separately for each dataset and estimates rolled up to create final estimates (Pollio *et al.*, 2006).

3.3 Coverage error

3.3.1 Problem

Coverage errors occur when the target population does not fully match with the population actually sampled. The source of the coverage error may be an inadequate sampling frame or flaws in the implementation of the data collection. Coverage error may take two forms: *undercoverage* (when members of the target population are excluded) or *overcoverage* (when units are included erroneously). Both undercoverage and overcoverage may distort inference based on descriptive or analytical statistics.

This is particularly the case if the cause of the coverage error is correlated with the characteristics being measured.

Coverage error often emerges in studying hard-to-reach populations, as the risk that relatively large parts of the target populations are missing from the sampling frames is high amongst those groups. In some cases, there is no sampling frame available or the population is hard to identify. Factors such as tenuous legal status, stigma or distrust may lead to misreporting when respondents are asked to identify themselves as belonging to a population (e.g. Roma). This measurement error in turn produces coverage error (Lyberg *et al.*, 2014).

3.3.2 Measures to reduce coverage error

Measures that can be taken to ensure that ‘hard to reach’ groups are adequately covered in sample frames are discussed separately for general and specific population surveys.

With respect to *general population surveys*, the problem of non-coverage in the main sampling frame can be tackled by multi-frame sampling.⁵ Whereas most survey samples are selected from a single sampling frame that presumably covers all of the units in the target population, multiple-frame sampling refers to surveys in which two or more frames are used and independent samples are respectively drawn from each of the frames. Inferences about the target population are based on the combined sample data. An example of multi-frame sampling is the combination of address frames with telephone number lists. Where applicable and available, further supplementary frames could take the form of registers or membership lists obtained from organisations representing the interests of particular ‘hard to reach’ groups (e.g. non-governmental organisations representing the poor, refugees, etc.). A limitation in the use of multi-frame sampling, however, is that it tends to increase variance (Behrens *et al.*, 2008).

With respect to *specific population surveys*, in instances where an appropriate sample frame does not exist, a variety of rare population sampling techniques can be applied. One technique is to screen a large representative sample from which certain types of respondents can be selected. However, this is an expensive exercise, particularly when the rare population sought represents a small proportion of the sampled population. Other important techniques to sample hard-to-reach populations have been extensively discussed in Chapter 2.

3.4 Undercounts

3.4.1 Problem

A census faces serious obstacles in counting certain segments of the population. The undercount affects hard-to-reach populations in particular, such as ethnic minorities and homeless people. Estimating census undercount is an important aspect of the statistical profiling of subpopulations that are hard to survey. Although such groups may represent a relatively small proportion of the population, they may contribute disproportionately to the overall undercount.

Undercounts are not only an obstacle in the case of census counts. The problem can also arise when making estimates for the entire population based on a sample. In Section 1.2.4.3, we referred to the study by David and Snijders (2002), where snowball sampling was used to estimate the size of the homeless population in Budapest in the period 1996-1998. In addition to the snowball method, which was used for the year 1997, the researchers used two different capture-recapture samples to

⁵ The method is referred to as dual-frame sampling when the survey uses two frames.

estimate the number of homeless. The first capture-recapture sample was based on the lists of homeless people who were screened under the ‘Tuberculosis programme’ in three consecutive years (from 1996 to 1998). The second data set includes three complete lists for the year 1996.

Table 3.1 gives an overview of the total number of places available for the homeless in Budapest and estimates of the homeless population from 1996 to 1998 using the snowball and the two capture-recapture methods.

Table 3.1 The total number of places available for the homeless and estimates of the homeless population from 1996 to 1998

	1996	1997	1998
Total number of places available for the homeless in Budapest	3,410	3,578	3,632
Snowball estimate		4,097	
Capture-recapture estimates			
Data set 2	6,519		
Data set 1		16,959	

Source David and Snijders (2002)

Although the estimates relate to different years, it can be seen that there is a large discrepancy between (a) the estimates based on the snowball sample and Data set 2 of the capture-recapture method on the one hand and (b) the estimate based on Data set 1 of the capture-recapture method on the other hand. According to David and Snijders, the discrepancy can be explained by the different sampling method used in Data set 1. Moreover, the relatively low estimate based on the snowball sample is considered to be a result of the clustering effect: Since this population is quite segregated not only from the non-homeless population but internally as well, the respondents of the initial sample mostly included other homeless people from the same place where they themselves usually appear or spend the night. The relatively low rate of fluctuation hinders the formation of new connections resulting in lower estimates compared to other methods. The significant difference between the estimates of homeless numbers in the aforementioned study demonstrates the difficulties in covering hard-to-reach populations without having undercounts (David & Snijders, 2002).

3.4.2 Measures to estimate undercounts

Several methods can be used to estimate undercounts in order to increase the reliability of one’s own estimates. The same methods can be used for measuring census undercounts. Given that the hard-to-reach populations are often not (sufficiently) included in census counts, these methods can contribute to a more accurate coverage of those groups. Potentially useful methods to control for undercounts include the administrative record match, demographic analysis, reverse record check and post-enumeration survey.

3.4.2.1 Administrative record match

An administrative record match (ARM) is an evaluation procedure in which a sample from the administrative record file is matched case-by-case to the census population or subpopulation of interest. For the ARM to be a viable approach, the government administration has to possess a high quality records system for the (sub)population of interest. In some cases, the country has a centralised administrative record system that contains records for nearly all the residents. In other cases, the country has to merge several administrative records to cover the entire population of interest.

An important advantage in the light of this topic is that ARM allows focusing on the hard-to-survey segments of the population. In Norway, the ARM method was used to evaluate the records for immigrants and foreign-born Norwegians on Norway’s Central Population Register (CPR) (Mulry,

2014). In Belgium, the National Register of natural persons was used to conduct research on former asylum seekers over the period 2001-2010. Although the information of the register is primarily collected for administrative purposes, it can also be used to produce statistics (Rea *et al.*, 2014). The ARM method also comes with disadvantages since there is no guarantee that the administrative list or lists cover the entire population of interest.

3.4.2.2 Demographic analysis

Demographic analysis uses analytical techniques applied to aggregate population data to study populations and estimate their size. The data used for demographic analysis combine birth, death, and immigration rates; sex ratios, life expectancy tables; historical series of census data; and data from sample surveys. In order to apply demographic analysis, a country has to have high-quality historical series for each of these quantities where the consistency of the different series has been confirmed.

A disadvantage of demographic analysis is that the estimates are possible only for subgroups identified in the vital records. For instance, in the US population estimates were possible for only two racial groups (blacks and non-blacks) because the historical records put people in only those two categories. In recent years, the records have been adapted to include the category of Hispanic ethnicity.

3.4.2.3 Reverse record check

A reverse record check (RRC) is a census evaluation program in which a sample of the population is drawn from records that existed before the census, traced forward to the time of the (subsequent) census, and matched to the census. The frame is usually composed of people enumerated in the previous census, persons missed in the previous census, births and migration. The difference with the ARM approach is that the records from the last census are not generally classified as administrative records. This type of records sample is likely to have a better coverage than a census.

A potential problem related to the research of hard-to-reach populations is that the availability of updated addresses for the people in the records sample is a key requirement for implementing RRC. Especially in the case of homeless people, this might be difficult to comply with. Another potential disadvantage is that even if hard-to-enumerate groups were easier to sample several years before the census, this advantage may be offset to some extent by some kind of attrition bias, with subgroups who were traced more successfully in the past also being more likely to be counted in the census than those who could not be traced.

3.4.2.4 Post-enumeration survey

A post-enumeration survey (PES) is a survey conducted after a census for the purpose of measuring census coverage. The survey respondents are matched to the census on a case-by-case basis. The PES method thus allows the researchers to find individuals missed by the census. A comparison of the census to the PES estimate of population size yields the undercount rate.

A key condition of the PES method is that inclusion in the coverage survey should be independent of inclusion in the census. Unfortunately, the likelihood that individuals from hard-to-reach groups, such as homeless people, are missed by both the PES and the census count is relatively high (Mulry, 2014).

3.5 Conclusion

The problems in collecting high-quality data from hard-to-reach populations are diverse and often interrelated. Non-response, coverage error and undercounts are measurement errors that can emerge in all types of research. However, given the potential obstacles in studying hard-to-reach populations

presented in Chapter 1, the related bias can be more significant compared to research on other populations. For researchers on hard-to-reach populations it is important to be aware of these sources of error, as well as the methods to minimise them.

During each stage of the planning, there may be new insights about the feasibility of the survey design, leading to repeated revisions of the research goals, the definition of the target population, the questionnaire, sampling design, training procedures, mode choice, and so on. Ideally, the design chosen should be one that produces estimates with the smallest possible mean squared errors. This criterion leads to a design that takes all major sources of error into account. This implies that any organisation conducting surveys must have a system for quality assurance and quality control in place.

4. Enhancing trust and communicative success

In Chapter 1, we concluded that difficulties in reaching poor populations are sometimes the result of a cultural or linguistic mismatch between the different stakeholders in the research process, leading to mistrust *vis-à-vis* researchers and ‘discursive dissonance’ (Pan & Lubkemann, 2014) between researchers/interviewers and respondents. In order to overcome this mismatch and to realise ‘communicative success’ (Pan & Lubkemann, 2014), several authors suggest to work out strategies which are able to enhance trust towards researchers within the target group and to remove cultural and/or linguistic barriers (for instance Lyberg *et al.*, 2014 for an overview of the literature). To this end, five widely adopted strategies could be identified in the literature on poverty:

- doing (community-based) participatory research;
- recruiting peer researchers or interviewers;
- providing training, support and supervision for interviewers;
- elaborating culturally appropriate questionnaires;
- developing innovative data collection methods.

Community-based participatory research is considered as an approach or a paradigm of how research ought to be organised, rather than a specific research method for data collection and analysis. This strategy should be applied at every stage, from the designing of the project, (including the identification of issues to be studied and the conceptual and operational definition of variables), over the recruitment of respondents and the data collection, the analysis and formulation of conclusions – up to the dissemination of the results. The other mentioned strategies are mostly, but not exclusively, confined to the data collection phase. Preferably, they must be applied in combination to produce the best outcomes.

4.1 Strategy 1: doing (community-based) participatory research

Participatory research, known in the US as community-based participatory research (CBPR), has been developed as a critical reaction against conventional research practice, in which researchers enter a community, collect data, and leave without generating benefits for the community or indeed depict the community in a negative way. As an alternative to research approaching the community members solely as object of inquiry, participatory research aims to overcome power imbalances by including the community into the research process (Beebejaun *et al.*, 2014) and giving the community members more authority, control and influence in the research (Bennett & Roberts, 2004). In the US, participatory research has been applied mostly in public health research, and almost exclusively in poor or oppressed communities (Morgan, 2010), notably in research about minority health (Green & Mercer, 2001). Within these communities, it expresses and puts into practice ‘the belief that people in poverty have a right to participate in analysing their own situation and how to tackle it’ (Bennett & Roberts, 2004). So, in contrast to traditional descriptive approaches, participatory research, and in particular action research, aims at transformation through empowerment, i.e. to alter the social conditions in which the community finds itself (Beebejaun *et al.*, 2014).

Although the ethos of participatory research is built on the conviction that collaboration, co-creation and coproduction lead to mutual trust between the researcher and the researched community and realise a more all-round, in-depth honest research product and real transformational outcomes,

it turns out that in practice the level of involvement differs greatly from one research project to another. In that respect, Bennett and Roberts (2004) prefer to speak about a continuum of participation in which ‘different numbers of people may be involved in one or more stages of the research process, and to a greater or lesser degree.’ In the same vein, Laderchi (2001) distinguishes between three main conceptualisations of participation underpinning the different applications of participatory research: discourses of participation emphasising self-determination (research done *by* the people), efficiency (research done *for* the people) and mutual learning (research done *with* the people). The first two discourses can be considered as the poles along the participation continuum, with researcher-led inquiry (efficiency) at one end - in which participation can be limited to consultation and, community-led inquiry (self-determination) at the other end - in which the community has control over the entire research process (from the design of the project to the analysis of the data). Moreover, community-led participatory research differs most from conventional research by emphasising shared ownership of research projects, community-based analysis of social problems and orientation towards community action (Kemmis & Mc Taggart, 2000). The mutual learning discourse on participation finds itself between these two poles, and differs from the other perspectives by prioritising collaboration between the researcher and the community and coproduction of knowledge during one or more stages of the research process.

Depending the chosen discourse, the operationalisation of the participatory research will take different directions regarding key issues. The first issue concerns the role or the position of the researcher in the project. In contrast to researcher-led inquiries, the literature emphasises that co-productive research projects and community-led research project have deeply challenged the traditional conceptualisation of the researcher as an expert who is objectively describing and explaining the reality under scrutiny (Beebeejaun *et al.*, 2014). For example, in community-led research the role of the researcher may be limited to facilitating the research process in support of the community members conducting and leading the research, while in coproductive research both parties bring into the exchange process their - in principal equally valued - sources and methods of knowledge production and expertise. Certainly, in both operationalised forms, the researcher will inevitably (partly) lose control over the research process. This is not the case in researcher-led inquiries in which community members are only consulted or approached as suppliers of information (for instance by using advisory groups of community members), but in which the researcher always keeps the lead in the research process (Bennett & Roberts, 2004). The other, related issue concerns the question to what extent participatory research should be introduced in the different stages of the research process. When applying community-led research rigorously, the use of participatory research throughout the entire research process seems self-evident, while in researcher-led inquiries, the use of participatory research methods will mostly be limited to the stages where participation of community members is expected to improve the efficiency of the research or to diminishing non-response rates.

Although it is at the core of the participatory research ethos, according to Bennett and Roberts (2004), community-led poverty research has been less frequently used than collaborative and researcher-led inquiries, as participatory poverty research is, in practice, ‘limited mostly to exploring the effects of poverty on them, with the research agenda still being set by outside researchers’ and to researchers mostly coming back in the data analysis stage, preventing involvement of people living in poverty in making sense of the information. Other studies (Beebeejaun *et al.*, 2014; Warr *et al.*, 2011) come to similar conclusions when stating that in the analysed case studies only partial participation or a selective adaptation of participatory research is achieved. If selectively adapted, research projects on poverty may thus be designed as community-led or collaborative at one stage (for instance by using peer interviewers for the data collection stage), but researcher-led at another stage (for instance by using standardised and highly structured instruments that allowed only minimal modification after consultation). In our view, this partial and selective operationalisation of participatory research not only indicates that researchers are in the midst of the uncertainty of how to tackle ‘epistemological challenges that are arising from the existence of multiple world views’ (Umemoto, 2001). They also

make clear how researchers are trying to deal with traditional academic output norms (such as publishing in peer-reviewed journals) that are reliant on the conceptualisation of the researcher as objective expert (Beebeejaun *et al.*, 2014) or with expectations of commissioners or policy makers. In that respect, Kelleher and Quirke (2014) rightly emphasise that academic researchers conducting participatory research are always challenged to ‘meet a point of triangulated consensus’ in the midst of sometimes conflicting agendas.

Nevertheless, inclusive collaborative participatory research projects exist. An interesting example was the three-year project of ATD, called ‘Merging of Knowledge’ that started in 1996 in France and Belgium (Research Group Fourth World-University, 2007).⁶ The aim of the project was ‘to produce new knowledge and understanding out of the fight against persistent poverty, based on academic knowledge, knowledge gained from experience and knowledge gained through action’ (Bennett & Roberts, 2004). Therefore, 15 people experiencing poverty, 12 academics and five full-time staff (‘volunteers’) from ATD Fourth World were brought together and supported by a team of adult teachers and an advisory group. For 22 months, the project members with a personal experience of poverty met three days each week in subgroups of three persons to discuss five research themes (history, family, knowledge and learning, work and citizenship). Parallel to the meeting sessions, every two months, a three-days seminar and thematic groups were planned for the collective research. The advisory group had the right to intervene when different views appeared to conflict. Bennett and Roberts (2004) point out that the intensive sharing of human experiences was ‘vital for the participants to find common ground in spite of their very diverse backgrounds and lives.’ Therefore, the project was able to change the lives of those who were involved or to change academic research and teaching about poverty. Nevertheless, the project proved to be no easy experience, facing problems of time and resources.

In such mixed research teams including academics, social workers and individuals from vulnerable target groups, the organisation of dialogical research requires specific methodological rules to guarantee a ‘genuine’ triangulation and avoid biases generated by imbalances in power and communication skills. The experimental methodological framework involved the following key principles:

- positive discrimination in the allocation of time and resources, with priority being given to the weakest participants in the process (three days per week for the activists versus half a day for the academics);
- effective investment in the research capacity of those groups (teachers, coaches, advisory group);
- adaptation of analytical instruments and language;
- culture-sensitive approaches, including mediation and training of all participants for better mutual understanding;
- methodological flexibility, with more weight being given to dialogical and reflexive approaches among the activists, versus more desk research among the academics;
- joint (voluntary) involvement of all parties until the end of the research, including joint formulation/approval of the conclusions and co-authorship of the publications.

In the next paragraphs, we analyse in depth other widely adopted strategies to overcome barriers between researchers and the target group. Although, in most cases, the use of these strategies implies a shift to participatory research to a greater or lesser degree, they never guarantee a fully operationalised or inclusive participative research design. We therefore suggest that each research project on poverty integrating one of these strategies should be explicit about its aims and underpinning participation ethos, ‘rather than allowing limitations of time and money to dictate choices about participation.’ (Bennett & Roberts, 2004)

⁶ See http://4thworldmovement.org/publications_wp/merging-knowledge/ - and for more recent ‘pooling of knowledge’ projects: <http://unheard-voices.org/category/croisement-des-savoirs/?lang=en>.

4.2 Strategy 2: recruiting peer researchers or interviewers

The term *peer* means that researchers, collectors or interviewers in a survey project are from the same cultural, ethnic or linguistic background as the target group members. The use of peer researchers or interviewers is believed to provide better access to hard-to-reach communities and to establish trust within members of the target group, particularly non-native groups, as it is easier to understand and trust interviewers or collectors who have the same cultural, ethnic or linguistic background or live in the target geographic area. In the 2011 American Census, for example, mixed teams of ethnic interviewers broadly reflecting the ethnic mix of the population were therefore recruited (Abbott & Compton, 2014). To find Korean-American participants for community-partnered health promotion research, Han *et al.* (2007) formed a research team including first-generation Korean immigrant researchers and staff who understood the culture and language of the target group and shared immigrant experiences. According to Han *et al.* (2007) this strategy enabled the team 'to identify a wide range of barriers to Korean participation in health promotion studies and suggest solutions to problems that would have otherwise kept some Koreans from participation'.

The use of peer interviewers is also widely adopted in community-based poverty research, where peer interviewers are recruited for conducting face-to-face interviews. In this paragraph, we present two papers (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014; Warr *et al.*, 2011) which describe the implementation of the peer-interviewing method in a survey among hard-to-reach poor populations. The first study, the All Ireland Traveller Health Study (AITHS), consists of a comprehensive consultation process on the Traveller health status and health needs of all Travellers living in Ireland (North and South). For the survey, a regional and national network of (female) peer researchers had been created to act as a key link between Travellers, Traveller organisations and the study team at University College Dublin. Within this network, 400 Travellers were recruited and trained as peer researchers (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014). The second study builds on the experience of peer interviewers 'involved in collecting local data for urban regeneration projects undertaken in the most socioeconomically disadvantaged locales in Victoria, Australia.' (Warr *et al.*, 2011). The involved peer interviewers were all residents of the same local communities as their respondents.

From these case studies, the following key lessons for the operationalisation of peer-interviewing in surveys could be drawn:

- to be successful, the engagement of peer interviewers needs to be framed in an inclusive, collaborative or community-led perspective on participation. In the Irish study (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014), the study team chose to include Traveller community participation and ensured a sense of 'ownership' from design to dissemination. Recruiting peer interviewers rather than outside interviewers was viewed as a self-evident consequence of this choice. According to Warr *et al.* (2011), the only (partly) participative Australian Health study set limits to the participatory potential of peer interviewing in this setting. For example, peer interviewing combined with a very standardised and non-tailored survey questionnaire led to interviewer frustrations 'with the length and complexity of the survey form with its 'governmentish' language, difficulties capturing and recording open-ended responses and challenges with time management in keeping the interview 'on track'' (Warr *et al.*, 2011). When correctly applied, including peer interviewers implies that professional researchers from the university have to be willing to relinquish exclusive control over the research process. This is not always an easy task, as it can be hard for academic field researchers 'to feel somewhat isolated from the raw data, because we had not conducted the interviews' (Benoit *et al.*, 2005);
- in the Ireland Travellers' study, the recruitment of peer interviewers or researchers was facilitated by building on existing projects, such as for example the Pavee Point Travellers in Ireland whose members were used to work together with members of the majority population (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014). Without this opportunity, the chance of recruiting peer researchers would have been compromised from the start;

- for a successful implementation of the strategy, it is critical to offer the peer researchers or interviewers training, on-going support and supervision in developing the necessary interviewing skills and knowledge of the study aims and design (see next paragraph for an in-depth discussion);
- in practice, proximity between peer interviewers and interviewees may act as a double-edged sword. On the one hand, proximity encourages interviewees to participate in the community survey and gives researchers access to insider information, resulting in a more valid data collection. On the other hand, the Australian study points out that proximity limits preservation of confidentiality in ongoing relationships or objectivity in the face of disagreeable opinions, sometimes compromising trust. Interesting interview data may not have been collected because the peer interviewer tended to regard some responses of the interviewee as trivial or as ‘old hat’ (Elliot *et al.*, 2002). Furthermore, being an insider also means that after completion of the interview, the interviewers return to their everyday role in the community. Therefore, peer interviewers risk more than outside researchers ‘a blurring of the lines between their roles as community interviewers (researchers) and being members of the community being interviewed (participants/subjects).’ To avoid this blurring of insider-outsider borderlines, the continuous moving in and out of their different roles requires considerate and careful navigation as much as possible (for instance by creating peer support teams);
- in both studies, the personal benefits for the peer interviewers or researchers are also stressed. Mentioned benefits include empowerment, increased self-confidence, getting a fee per interview, improved language or other work-related skills, and increased involvement in the neighbourhood or community organisation. As such, recruiting peer interviewers for surveying hard-to-reach populations has the potential to change the poor community from within;
- peer interviewers do not only influence the data collection because of aspects of their self-identity, but may themselves be emotionally touched by the gathered information. For example, Benoit *et al.* (2005) who engaged former sex workers as peer researchers experienced that, in these cases, the interview process might evoke an emotional response from the personal history. They found a way around this problem by providing peer support ‘that included two transcribers’ working side by side and having each other for companionship when handling sensitive material.’ (see also next strategy).

4.3 Strategy 3: providing interviewers training, on-going support and supervision

According to Billiet and Loosveldt (1988) interviewer training, in general, helps improving the quality of survey data by reducing item nonresponse, increasing the amount and accuracy of information obtained, and increasing survey participation by teaching interviewers how to identify and handle respondents’ concerns. Interviewer training for surveying hard-to-reach groups can be applied for a wide range of interviewers: peer interviewers, outside interviewers hired for the data collection, and members of the university research team. Nevertheless, the design of the training needs to be tailored to the needs of the interviewers and to lead to a better fit between the interviewer and the interviewee. In that respect, peer interviewers benefit most from training in research skills, while outside interviewers need supplementary training increasing their cultural sensitivity or awareness *vis-à-vis* the target group. Training should also help to develop general personal competences which have turned out as the most important for interviewing hard to reach groups, such as a professional, non-judgmental and empathetic attitude (Draus *et al.*, 2005).

Few studies on poverty describe the content and operationalisation of training programs (see Lyberg *et al.*, 2014 for a short overview, and for instance Elliot *et al.*, 2002; O’Hegarty *et al.*, 2010; Benoit *et al.*, 2005; Becker *et al.*, 2014). Regarding the content of the program, interviewer training sessions included three key elements: an introduction to the study (in order to enable the interviewers in shortly describing the study to the interviewers), sessions on interviewing techniques and interviewing exercises (demonstration, role-play with feedback and discussion).

Regarding the design of training programmes for peer interviewers, we note that the AIHS-study team (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014) opted for a two-stage training programme. First, 85 coordinators and assistant coordinators of the regional and national networks or organisations were trained. In this six-day course a trainers training and the development of the study instruments and protocols was included, so that in a next step, these 85 coordinators were able to train in turn 400 Travellers at the local level as peer researchers. In his case study on the CARES research project (United Kingdom), which was intended to increase research literacy and promote participatory health research in minority communities, Morgan (2010) refers to the ‘academy’ approach with a 15-weeks training programme of the peer interviewers (called CARES Fellows). In this training programme, the Fellows received a relatively quick umbrella survey course of research methodology, leading to a certificate of completion. This approach was chosen in order to enable the collaborative team of researchers and community members ‘to begin speaking the same research language’ (Morgan, 2010). At the end of this stage, the CARES Fellows applied their research knowledge by working together on the design of a survey instrument around a topic they had chosen (namely obesity and nutrition). Morgan also mentions some areas of concern. First, because of the demanding schedule of the program, from the 19 starters only 13 members of minority communities completed the study. Moreover, the cohort of Fellows was fairly well educated and worked as nurses, social workers or teachers, indicating that the programme assumed a certain level of literacy and that, with the exception of their minority status, the ‘peer’ character of the interviewers was rather limited. Morgan (2010) also notes that the ‘process required a great amount of lead time before any genuine process of investigation could begin’.

Because trust barriers between outside interviewers or researchers and hard-to-reach group members are likely to occur, Lyberg *et al.* (2014) suggest that these interviewers or researchers need more training and ongoing support than interviewers in other survey projects, in particular in cultural sensitivity and awareness or in coping with unexpected emotions coming up when faced with extreme poverty situations (see also Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014). Sufficient time for training should therefore be scheduled and budgeted in the research proposal. Although the importance of training could not be underrated, we nevertheless found few studies where training for outside interviewers or (need for) support by experienced interviewers was mentioned (Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014). An interesting exception to this general finding is the paper of Malam, Everson and Davies (2014) on the English national survey of people with intellectual disabilities, in which the content of the interviewer training sessions has been described. The interactive training sessions, aimed to increase awareness on the lives of people with intellectual disabilities, were run by CEPF, a self-advocacy group: ‘In the first session they asked interviewers to think about the importance and mechanics of speaking up in their own lives, and how they thought this would differ for people with intellectual disabilities. The second session looked more generally at the lives of people with intellectual disabilities, with interviewers encouraged to ask questions to raise their awareness of the issues facing this group of people. The final session looked more specifically at the issues that they might encounter during the interviews’ (Malam *et al.*, 2014). Issues addressed included accessibility of questions, enhancing mutual trust and giving respondents space and time to answer.

References to cultural awareness training or supervision for research staff were also difficult to find (with Dumka *et al.*, 1997; Kelleher & Quirke, 2014 as exceptions). Dumka *et al.* (1997), for example, mention in their study on high-risk minority parents in America that all members of the research staff participated in a mandatory half-day cultural sensitivity workshop and received extensive weekly supervision: ‘The goal of this workshop for staff members was to become aware of their cultural biases and to clearly communicate our expectation that staff members would treat each other and participating families with respect’. The following reasons may explain why studies elaborate so rarely on training, support and supervision for interviewers and research staff:

- when faced with a lack of funding - a recurring theme in the hard-to-reach literature - the training and supervision component may be sacrificed in favour of other components which are considered as more essential (Lyberg *et al.*, 2014; Morgan, 2010);
- following more conventional ideas on research, members of the university research staff may consider themselves as interview experts and thus not in need of training;
- descriptions of training procedures and strategies are missed, simply because they have not yet been developed (Lyberg *et al.*, 2014).

4.4 Strategy 4: working to culturally appropriate questionnaires

Whatever the topic or aim, the task of the survey designer is to develop a series of standardised questions to obtain the necessary information from the respondents. Generally, researchers assume a correspondence between respondents and survey designers or interviewers with respect to the used language and concepts, with respect to an utterance's meaning⁷ and with respect to the aim and relevance of the survey. However, several authors found out that when surveying (minority) groups living in poverty, this correspondence could not be easily achieved, resulting in a high non-response rate or drop-out during the interview. For example, Nicaise and Schockaert (2014) note that even after adapting the survey in order to enhance the comparability between the EU-SILC statistics and the target groups, a sufficient degree of correspondence appeared to be more difficult to achieve than expected: 'Very poor people seem to have such a different life experience that for them a survey tuned to the average household can become surprisingly hard to answer. Many basic concepts do not exist or have a different meaning in the context of marginalised groups' (for similar conclusions, see Pan & Lubkemann, 2014; Golub, Strickler & Dunlap, 2012; Glasser, Hirsch & Chan, 2014). In what follows, we describe some specific strategies to achieve communicative success when surveying (minority) groups living in poverty. Communicative success is achieved when interviewers or the survey show the ability 'to obtain the information from respondents that the questionnaire and interview protocol were designed to elicit' (Pan & Lubkemann, 2014).

In several studies on poverty, questionnaire designers have modified existing questionnaires (such as EU-SILC, Census, State ATS etc.) to better capture the varied and unique cultural and social experiences of the target group members (see for instance O'Hegarty *et al.*, 2010; Kelleher & Quirke, 2014; Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014). To this end, they have developed similar procedures (Lyberg *et al.*, 2014):

- revision of the questionnaire by an expert advisory panel (O'Hegarty *et al.*, 2010), by the members of the target group (Kelleher & Quirke, 2014) or after qualitative or ethnographic research within the target group (Golub, Strickler & Dunlap, 2012; Glasser, Hirsch & Chan, 2014). For example, Kelleher and Quirke (2014) circulated the draft questionnaire to the Traveller organisations and posted it on the study website. In general, the revision may take several rounds of consultation and adaptation, based on the received feedback. Nicaise and Schockaert (2014) also note that adaptation of the EU-SILC questionnaire not only implied that the wording of questions was modified, but that new questions or modules, relevant to the target group, were included;
- if necessary, the revised questionnaire is translated into the (native) language spoken by the target group and cognitively tested;
- pre-testing of the survey by interviewers, resulting in further adaptations of the survey and better or clearer guidelines for interviewers based on the interviewer's feedback. In several cases, the pre-testing led to a shortened version of the survey as interviewers had experienced that the length of the response time increased the drop-out rate during the interview (for instance Kelleher & Quirke, 2014).

⁷ Pan & Lubkemann (2014) define utterance's meaning as 'the extent to which recipients understand an utterance to mean what the speaker intends it to mean' or the correspondence between the 'perceived meaning' and the 'speaker intended meaning' (Braun & Harkness, 2005).

In traditional poverty studies, especially on minority groups, survey adaptations are mostly considered as a translation which implies ‘finding the terminological equivalents and ‘plugging these in’ to a question whose phrasing should be otherwise minimally altered’ (Pan & Lubkemann, 2014). Harkness (2003) calls this the ‘Ask-the-Same-Question’ model. Pan and Lubkemann (2014) criticise this approach, stating that if concepts are socially constructed, literal translations will appear as insufficient, i.e. the questions will remain odd or unclear for the respondent. Therefore, they suggest to pay more attention to ‘the process of asking questions, or what might be termed the ‘performative’ aspect of communication’ (Pan & Lubkemann, 2014), as multiple observations of interviewer-respondent encounters showed that discursive dissonance was often rooted in different views between interviewers and respondents on the interview as a social interaction. For example, while the interviewer considered the interview as limited to the narrow task of information exchange, some respondents could only proceed with the interview after a certain degree of personal connection and in-groupness (see for other examples, Pan & Lubkemann, 2014). Furthermore, they show that communicative success was often and paradoxically the result of (bilingual) interviewers deviating from established protocol instead of clinging to the protocol, indicating that ‘differentiated stimulus inputs (the question or utterance verbalised by the interviewers) at some level are methodologically indispensable and actually required in order to achieve commensurable stimulus outputs (the information received by the respondent or communicative effect) across all segments of a population’ (Pan & Lubkemann, 2014). In that respect, successful culturally sensitive surveying requires not only adaptations before the interview, but also during the interview, and asks for well-trained (or bilingual) interviewers who know when and to which extent they have to modify the question without losing comparability.

4.5 Strategy 5: developing innovative data collection methods

4.5.1 Beyond-text methods

Most poverty research is based on formalised, specialist text-based data collection methods, such as surveys, assuming that poor people are able or willing to articulate their individual perspectives with standardised words and text. Beebeejaun *et al.* (2014) criticise this assumption, arguing that text-based data collection methods are necessarily researcher-led. In contrast to text-based methods, they believe that beyond-text methods ‘can act as a point of difference, symbolising a research ethos as well as a set of tools for research which facilitate coproduction.’ In particular, research in communities with high levels of illiteracy, with a rich oral tradition (for instance Travellers) or with high levels of economic stress (IOM & NRC, 2011) may benefit from non-text tools. However, these mostly qualitative empirical tools do not necessarily have to replace survey research, but may exist in combination to survey research or may help modifying survey questionnaires into a more culturally appropriate design.

4.5.1.1 Storytelling or narrative interviewing

A first example of beyond-text data collection methods is storytelling or narrative interviewing. To get better insight into the views and lives of Travellers, who have a rich oral expertise, Kelleher and Quirke (2014) developed an oral-visual questionnaire. IOM and NRC (2011) note that in Spicer’s research on poor American Indians narrative data collection methods worked better with people living in the midst of chaos, because it is only by letting these people tell stories that they may construct meaning and find coherence in disorienting experiences of trauma and dislocation. Surveys, by contrast, require that respondents have already made sense of their experiences.

4.5.1.2 Visual research methods, with focus on photo voice

A second example of beyond-text data collection are visual beyond-text methods, including use of cartoons, hand-drawn images, photographs, art, dance and other forms of performance. For example, visual data collection methods have been used in poverty research to capture in a participatory way the views of poor people (for instance Sime, 2008) or minority groups (for instance Redwood, Gale & Greenfield, 2012 as an example of art-based research).

Photo voice is an interesting example of this research method, as it has been used several times in community-based participatory poverty research (see Strategy 1), ranging from research on Indigenous people (Castleden, Garvin, Huu-ay-aht First Nation, 2008), to research on homeless people (Radley, Hodgetts & Cullen, 2005), mothers with learning disabilities (Booth & Booth, 2003) and children living in poverty (Sime, 2008). Originally, 'photo voice had been designed as a method to use participants' photographs as a catalyst to engage participants (those typically with less power) and policy makers (those typically with more power) in group dialogue for social change' (Castleden *et al.*, 2008). Since then, several studies have amended the method. However, two central characteristics of the original approach have been kept: community members living in poverty had been given a camera to take photographs on a certain topic of research interest, after which these members get the opportunity to select and to explain where it was taken, why it was taken, and what it meant to them.

Reasons for using photo voice depend on the target group. By using visual research methods with children and young people, Sime (2008) for example wanted to build on the existing competencies of this group with complex media devices outside the school. In the *Serving child?* project (United Kingdom), the research team gave each participating child 'a camera to take photographs of services during a week'. Each child was free to choose which aspects they wanted to show, how many photographs they wanted to take and when to take them. After printing the photos, the child could select the photographs which they did not want the research team to see. Then, individual interviews with the children to explore their service experiences were conducted. During the interview, children took the lead, as they chose 'which photos to discuss, how long to spend on each photograph and what significance to give to each experience' (Sime, 2008). In that respect, using photographs with children may be a very useful tool because it is accessible for children and young people in poverty as well as increasing agency within this group. In their research on Indigenous people in Canada, Castleden *et al.* (2008) have reported similar benefits of this method, finding that the implementation of this method had resulted in balancing power, creating a sense of ownership, fostering trust, building capacity, and implementing a culturally appropriate research project in the community. According to the authors, the most important success factor was the implementation of a feedback loop during the project or the designing of an iterative process, which gave the community members the opportunity to give input at regular intervals throughout the project. In particular, the use of individual interviews soon after participants' photographs had been taken in combination with recurring community potluck dinners, during which posters consisting of a collage of participants' 'priority' photographs and associated narratives had been presented, were identified as an 'important way of not only generating informal community dialogue but also creating community ownership over the knowledge generated.' (Castleden *et al.*, 2008). To operationalise this iterative process, however, the data collection process had to be extended to six months and included an increased commitment of time and effort on the part of participants and researchers.

Although photo voice has evident advantages, Sime (2008) also notes an important ethical concern regarding the issue of content, as parents and other gatekeepers may feel offended by photos taken in private places, such as the home. In a similar vein, Castleden *et al.* (2008) found out 'that participants may struggle with the challenge of how to photograph non-tangible items or issues. Therefore, Sime (2008) decided to give families the right to exclude or to limit the use of photographs which they considered as inappropriate, even knowing that this solution, in turn, involves the risk of confining the agency of children by parents intervening in the selection of photographs. To deal with

this concern, Castleden *et al.* (2008) suggest including training sessions for participants and community members on the ethics and mechanics of photography, signed informed consent forms from any photographed individuals and member-checking and transcription verification at the start of the process.

4.5.2 Using digital technology

Most authors, who have experience with survey research engaging poor subpopulations, suggest that self-administered (web) surveys directed to individuals should be avoided, because of the difficulty to reach and engage individuals (see Chapter 1 for reasons). Instead, they propose to collect community-wide data that are gathered with interviewers in face-to-face encounters (see for a review of the literature, Bonevski *et al.*, 2014). In some cases, however, precisely the use of computer-assisted self-report or interviews may help to engage poor subpopulations in surveys.

Bryant *et al.* (2011) used computer administered self-report for assessing smoking status among a low socio-economic population in Australia. For this project, (only English speaking) people visiting a non-government, non-for-profit service organisation were invited by their caseworkers to complete a touch-screen computer administered health survey. Bryant *et al.* (2011) conclude that this data collection method appeared as ‘an accurate and acceptable method of assessing smoking status in a low-SES sample of smokers in a community setting, with a low rate of misclassification identified.’

Kelleher and Quirke (2014) note that they finally opted for computer-assisted personal interviewing in combination with a more conventional computer-assisted approach to collect survey data on the Travellers’ population in Ireland, as they had noticed that to tape-record the interviews still required intensive transcription and raised confidentiality concerns. The computer assisted interview consisted of a pre-designed electronic interview with visual cues and a recorded voiceover, provided by a Traveller, to overcome the literacy barrier. After completing, the interview could then directly be sent to the research team for analysis without causing additional transcription costs. In a similar way, IOM & NRC (2011) describe how the use of digital technology ‘has been shown to increase the validity on sensitive topics’ and to overcome trust barriers in a research on sexual activity and substance use within poor families, where respondents were given headsets and laptops to hear the questions through the headsets and could then answer the questions on the laptops.

4.6 Conclusion

In this chapter we proposed five research strategies to overcome trust barriers between researchers and respondents in poverty research: doing (community-based) participatory research, recruiting peer researchers, data collectors or interviewers, providing training, support and supervision for interviewers, developing culturally appropriate questionnaires and innovative data collection methods, such as non-verbal methods and methods using digital technology. When applied thoroughly, the strategies look promising in enhancing communicative success with hard-to-reach groups living in poverty and thus increasing the validity of research results. However, it has to be noted that successful implementation of these strategies may require more time, commitment and effort from researchers, service providers and community members than traditional (postal or web) questionnaires directed to individuals. In that respect, excellent, valid research on hard-to-reach poor subpopulations can only exist by virtue of sufficient budget and good mutual and well-maintained relationships between university teams and service organisations or (self-)advocacy groups.

It is worth reminding at this point that the term ‘participatory research’ – as a common principle aiming at trust-building with the academic research team and/or empowerment of disadvantaged communities – in practice covers a wide variety of methods and degrees of ownership. Participation

can be limited to the involvement of individuals from a disadvantaged target group in the data collection (which basically remains 'extractive'). At the other extreme, it can also mean co-determination of the research objectives and joint drafting – and indeed, follow-up - of the research.

Academics should not be blamed for limiting the participation of their target group to some aspects of the research: this depends on the objectives as well as time and budget constraints. What matters is that the extent, conditions and purpose of participation are transparent for all stakeholders.

5. General conclusion

This report investigated the obstacles encountered in survey research on hard-to-survey groups. We started with a typology of obstacles, building on Tourangeau (2014), and distinguishing between hard-to-sample, hard-to-identify, hard-to-contact, hard-to-persuade and hard-to-interview groups living in poverty. Each of these obstacles has specific reasons and necessitates distinct approaches to help overcome the barriers. Although perfect solutions do not exist, precautions can be taken at three levels: sampling process, data collection methods and statistical methods to minimise bias. This report provides an overview, including points of attention and references to more specialised literature.

The last section digs deeper by raising some key epistemological and ethical issues in poverty research. Do academic researchers take the questions that poor people are asking seriously? Are they willing to share control over the research process (not just the data collection process)? Who are the ultimate owners of the research results? This section highlights a few examples of good practice, challenging the assumption that objective research needs to remain strictly neutral and ‘distant’ from the research object. As qualitative and participatory research is gaining ground, this approach can help in getting closer to the core of the topic. Trust-building, mutual learning and good timing are essential conditions of success for a genuine partnership with the hardest-to-reach disadvantaged groups. We also emphasised that, as the perfect participatory research probably does not exist, it is preferable to be clear about the limits on participation than to create an illusion of it. Yet, it is clear that participatory research can strongly enhance the internal validity of the research, which is otherwise so hard to achieve with these target groups. Interestingly, the examples illustrate that participatory methods are not limited to qualitative research and can perfectly be applied in survey research too.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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